
Banyuwangi Gandrung Dance as a Source of Ideas for Creating Evening Wear with Embroidered *Gajah Oling* Motifs and Sequence

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Abstract

Gandrung Dance is an art form dominated by dance with a typical orchestra popular in the Banyuwangi area. Gandrung dance has also become a dance for welcoming guests at various arts events as well as state events, so it is not wrong that Banyuwangi is often nicknamed the City of Gandrung. Evening wear is evening party clothing using high quality materials complete with decorative accessories to make the clothing look luxurious. Based on wanting to introduce more about Gandrung dance ornaments and clothing which have high cultural and artistic value through the stylization process into evening dresses that can depict the beauty of Gandrung dance in the form of evening wear. The aim of this research is to describe the process and results of creating evening wear designs using embroidered *gajah oling* motifs and sequins using the idea of the Gandrung Banyuwangi dance. This research includes creation or development research, which uses the Practice-led Research method, which consists of 4 stages, including: (1) Pre-design, (2) Design, (3) Realization, (4) Presentation. The results of this research show that: (1) the process of creating evening wear designs using the idea of the Gandrung Banyuwangi dance as a source (2) The results of the creation are 3 evening wear consisting of 2 female evening wear designs and 1 male evening wear design, for women there are 2 looks where the look 1 there are 3 pieces consisting of a span skirt, draped skirt, bustier, capuchon shawl, the 2nd look consists of a bustier and a puffed skirt, the male fashion look is a vest and trousers.

Keywords: evening wear, gandrung dance, Banyuwangi

Abstrak

Tari gandrung merupakan bentuk kesenian yang didominasi tarian dengan orkestra khas populer di wilayah Banyuwangi. Tari gandrung juga telah menjadi tarian penyambutan tamu

di berbagai acara kesenian juga acara kenegaraan hingga tidak salah jika Banyuwangi sering dijuluki Kota Gandrung. Evening wear merupakan busana pesta malam dengan menggunakan bahan-bahan yang berkualitas tinggi lengkap dengan hiasan aksesoris sehingga menjadikan busana tersebut terlihat mewah. Berdasarkan ingin lebih mengenalkan bagaimana ornamen dan busana tari gandrung yang mempunyai nilai budaya dan seni yang tinggi dengan proses stilasi menjadi gaun malam yang bisa menggambarkan indahnya tarian gandrung dalam wujud evening wear. Tujuan penelitian ini adalah untuk mendeskripsikan proses dan hasil penciptaan desain evening wear dengan aplikasi bordir motif gajah oling dan payet dengan sumber ide tari gandrung Banyuwangi. Penelitian ini termasuk penelitian penciptaan atau pengembangan, yang menggunakan metode Practice-Ied Research, yang terdiri dari 4 tahap, meliputi: (1) Pra-perancangan, (2) Perancangan, (3) Perwujudan, (4) Penyajian. Hasil penelitian ini menghasilkan: (1) proses penciptaan desain evening wear dengan sumber ide tari gandrung Banyuwangi (2) Hasil penciptaan berupa 3 evening wear yang terdiri dari 2 desain evening wear female dan 1 desain evening wear male, untuk female ada 2 look dimana look 1 ada 3 pieces yang terdiri dari rok span, rok draped, bustier, selendang capuchon, look yang ke 2 terdiri dari bustier dan rok peplum, look busana male berupa vest dan celana panjang.

Kata Kunci: *evening wear, tari gandrung, Banyuwangi*

Introduction

Gandrung dance is a traditional dance typical of Banyuwangi, East Java and has been performed for hundreds of years. . The popular art of Banyuwangi emerged at the same time as the Tirtagondo or Tirta Arum forest was cleared to build the capital city of Blambangan as a replacement for Pangpang or Ulu Pangpang on the initiative of the first regent of Banyuwangi, Mas Alit, who was inaugurated on February 2, 1774 at Ulu Pangpang. Regarding the origins of this gandrung art, Joh Scholte in his paper, namely Gandroeng Van Banyuwangi (1926), Chapter Gandrung Men, among other things, wrote the following: Originally there was a young man named Marsan and he toured the villages together with musicians who played drums and flew. As winners of the game, they were finally given a prize in the form of rice which they carried in a bag.

The first known woman in love in history was Semi, Semi, a child who was ten years old at that time in 1895 from the couple Midin and Raminah. According to a believed story, at that time Semi was suffering from quite a serious illness. Everything has been done, including going to the shaman, but Semi has not recovered. So Semi's mother (Mak Midhah) made a vow like "Kadhung sira waras, sun dhadekaken Seblang, kadhung sing yo sing" (If you recover, I will make you Seblang, if not, it won't happen). Apparently, in the end, Semi recovered and became a singer and started a new chapter by being danced by women. Gandrung in the name of this dance is interpreted as the fascination of the agrarian people of Blambangan with Dewi Sri as the Goddess of Rice and bringing prosperity to the community

The clothing and ornaments of the Banyuwangi gandrung dancers are quite distinctive and different from the clothing from other Javanese regional dances. Each piece of clothing

has a symbolic value related to the journey of gandrung dance in the past. One of the characteristics of gandrung dancers' clothing is the gajah oling motif. The gajah oling motif pattern is a plant design featuring an elephant's trunk on a white cloth backing. According to Ratnawati (2010), the gajah oling motif combines plants and animals which essentially represent the prosperous and amazing natural surroundings of Banyuwangi.

Sri Widarwati (1993) states that party clothes are made from high quality materials and decorations that attract attention. Evening party clothing is clothing that is different from other clothing starting from pattern making, material selection, fabric texture, cutting and decoration. Evening party clothing is unique and special in its manufacture, apart from that, evening party clothing also pays attention to neatness, detail, beauty and harmony so that it makes evening clothing look attractive. It is not surprising that evening clothing has a high selling value.

According to Syahrul (1999), embroidery is a decorative technique that uses an embroidery machine or computer embroidery machine to make various clothing accessories. It concentrates on the beauty and color composition of threads in different fabric media. The embroidery design pattern itself may have an impact on the shape of the three-dimensional embroidery application. Seherono (2011) said that a motif is an arrangement of various lines, shapes, colors and figures, or forms that are arranged naturally, with aesthetic value originating from ideas or imagination. The stylized gajah oling motif was used in this research. Features groove shapes, such as question marks or the letter "s" depicting an elephant's trunk and side rows with plant growth.

Maya and Coly (2007), say that sequins, on the other hand, are small decorations that are sewn on clothes. Embroidery itself is a sewing technique with decorative purposes using thread, hand sewing needles, and decorations (which can be sequins, beads, and the like, stated by Delaa, 2013). A stitching technique known as sequin embroidery decorates fabric or clothing with sequins or small beads. This technique involves using a needle and thread to sew each sequin or bead onto the fabric in a specific pattern or design. Sequin embroidery is often used on formal wear such as wedding dresses, party dresses, and stage wear to add shine and more interesting details. An embroidery project including sequins requires a lot of time and effort to complete because the method requires precision and talent. (Alfitrah et al., 2024)

“Jagad Osing” culture, which will study Banyuwangi culture and customs, is tasked with designing fashion designs with big topics. The author raises one sub-theme, namely Gandrung dance, as a source of ideas for creating evening wear designs. With the background of wanting to introduce more about how Gandrung dance ornaments are stylized into evening dresses which can depict the beauty of Gandrung dance in the form of evening wear with embroidered gajah oling motifs and sequins which will add to the luxurious impression of the evening wear. (Kusuma et al., 2024)

In accordance with the research problem, the aim to be achieved in this research is to describe the creation process and describe the results of creating evening wear designs using embroidered gajah oling motifs and sequins with the source of the Banyuwangi gandrung dance idea.

Research Method

The systematic realization of a work is the definition of a research method. Stages of creating a work of art which outlines the design of the process of creating a work of art in accordance with the stages of creation from getting the inspiration (idea), designing, to realizing the work of art, according to Supendi, E., & Isnanta, S. D. (2020).

The research method used in this research is a work creation procedure with a Practice-Ied-Research approach or practical research, this research is research that leads to a new understanding of practice and it is put into practice with a focus on "Creating evening wear designs using embroidered the gajah oling motifs and sequins with the source of the Banyuwangi gandrung dance idea". Based on the description above, the Practice-Ied-Research research stages can be written as follows

Result and Discussion

This research includes creation or development research, which uses the Practice-Ied Research method, which consists of 4 stages, including: (1) Pre-design, (2) Design, (3) Realization, (4) Presentation. Pre-design, design, realization and presentation are research phases that are integrated with practice. According Hendriyana (2021), Practice-led Research is a scientific work that comes from ongoing practice research by creating new works through research and practice.

This method was applied in the creation of the work entitled "Banyuwangi Gandrung Dance as a Source of Ideas for Creating Evening Wear Designs with Embroidery of Gajah Oling Motifs and Sequins" with the following stages:

A. Exporation / Pre-design

Pre-design includes searching and identifying problems, extracting and collecting reference materials, processing and evaluating data to draw significant findings that form the basis of design solutions, and other activities aimed at exploring sources of ideas according to Gustami, (2007). Pre-design is also called the exploration stage, activities

include exploring sources of inspiration, data collection and references. At this stage the researcher looks for inspiration and information as a guide in determining the design concept to be created.

The design stage is the stage of creating a design plan for the product to be made. In this creation, the researcher created a moodboard and fashion design that refers to the moodboard and design concept. The realization stage is the stage of turning a product that has been designed into a real work. In this creation, the realization of the work goes through two stages, namely the realization in the form of a prototype and the realization of the work using actual materials. Presentation of the work is the final stage in the creation of the work. At this stage, the finished work can be published to the general public as a form of work promotion. This can take the form of exhibitions or certain events such as fashion shows. Apart from being published, the work that has been created can also be evaluated to ensure that the work that has been created is in accordance with the planned concept or theme.

1. Inspiration Source Exploration Stage

Look for inspiration that fits the big theme. Researchers develop imaginations that are correlated with predetermined major themes and sub-themes. In accordance with the big theme of the 2024 fashion event, Jagad Osing, a theme that highlights the culture and traditions of Banyuwangi with the sub-theme of Gandrung Banyuwangi dance being a source of ideas for creating evening fashion designs.. From the inspiration source image, the researcher observed the shape, texture, color, identity and target market.

The target market for this creation wear is men and women an age range of 20 – 30 years who like formal or semi-formal evening wear that looks elegant and luxurious, and have middle to upper income.

2. Design Concept Exploration Stage

Gather information that will provide a summary of the fashion design idea or concept that was ultimately realized. To ensure the goals and rules for producing a work, a moodboard is created. Evening wear moodboard with embroidered of gajah oling motifs and sequins with the idea of Gandrung Banyuwangi dance.

3. Exploration Stage Manipulating Fabric

After creating a design concept, the next step is to determine the fabric manipulation that will be applied in this creation. Developing sources of ideas for gandrung dance by exploring components of gandrung dance clothing such as sembong, ilat-ilat, kelat bahu, oncer and sampur with a stylization process realized in evening wear, with the Gajah Oling motifs added as decoration.

B. Work Design

1. Alternative Design

Alternative designs are all designs that are created and developed based on the source of ideas used. The number of alternative designs that will be created in this research is 10 (ten) men's (male) fashion designs and 20 (twenty) women's (female) fashion designs. The first part are 10 (ten) men's evening wear design before colouring and then follows by 10 (ten) men's evening wear design after colouring. The second part are 20 (twenty) women's evening wear design before colouring and then follows by 20 (twenty) women's evening wear after colouring.

2. Selected Design

The selection of the best designs was carried out by the supervising lecturer and a team of 3 (three) party fashion designs consisting of 2 (two) women's fashion designs and 1 (one) men's fashion design. Next, work drawings are created based on the assessment instruments that have been created. The assessment was carried out by three experts in the design and fashion fields.

3. Working Drawings

Working drawings or often known as technical drawings are techniques for drawing ideas in detail, before they become prototypes and are produced. Technical drawing is needed to minimize errors or missing details that will be made and has a function as a translator. Working drawings in the creation of ready to wear deluxe help in reading the details of the clothing design, all details of the clothing, including flat drawings, clothing sizes, details materials and colors used and even accessories. applied to clothing.

The material design contains plans regarding what materials will be used in clothing. Designing materials is very necessary to obtain material efficiency, ensuring the minimum material requirements required so that material shortages or excessive use of materials occur.

Production design 1 contains the design of the front and back of the evening wear with complete details of the design of the clothing. There are three production designs 1 with detailed parts

C. Realization of Work

The steps for realizing evening party clothing, clothes for men and women consist of several stages of the conversion process from design to product. Where the fashion design is made according to the design chosen by the supervisor. The stages of the work realization process are as follows:

1. Take body measurements

The ready to wear deluxe both men's clothing and women's clothing, production process starts from measuring the model's body during the model audition.

2. Make a pattern according to the design

After getting the required body measurements for male and female models, the next step is to make the pattern as follows:

a. Create a basic front and back body pattern

b. Create a broken front and back body pattern

c. Make the basic pattern of the front and back skirt

d. Create a broken front and back skirt pattern

e. Make a basic pattern for front and back trousers

f. Create a broken front and back trouser pattern

g. Making shawl and capuchon patterns

3. Placing the pattern on the material

Before placing the pattern on the material, there are several things that must be done, namely checking the texture of the material fibers and the direction of the material motif. Next, put the large pattern first, then the small pattern. Then the pattern is pinned with pins.

4. Cutting material

Cut the material according to the pattern markings which have marked cutting boundaries or seams.

5. Sewing clothing parts according to design

The process of sewing clothing with a sewing machine. This sewing process uses several sewing techniques that are used to make the perfect evening dress and involves combining materials that have been cut to create clothing according to the design.

6. Creating fabric manipulation

The process of making clothing decorations is by sewing embroidered *gajah oling* motifs and sewing sequin beads onto the clothing according to the design, various sequin embroidery techniques are used to obtain perfect results

7. Clothing Fittings.

In fashion design, the fitting stage is an important stage to ensure that the clothes not only look good aesthetically but are also comfortable when worn. In the process of realizing this work, two fittings were carried out, fitting 1 using a prototype and fitting 2 using actual materials. The process of fitting clothes according to the body shape of the 3 (three) models before the final finishing process. The next stage is evaluating the product from the validation results carried out by the supervisor

D. Review of Works

1. Work Description (1)

The first embodiment of evening party clothing for women (females) consisted of span skirts, draped skirts or wrapped skirts, bustiers and shawls that became one with the capucon. Material from luxury satin and chiffon fabric. Sequin decoration in the form of a fringer on the bustier and the addition of sequin beads on the skirt.

The design of the red bustier dress with sequin fringe decoration is inspired by the otok kemben gandrung dance costume with a sampur or shawl decorated with tassels. A red span skirt wrapped in a black wrapped skirt depicts a sexy and elegant outfit. Meanwhile, the capuchon and black scarf complement the beauty of the outfit, adding to the simple, elegant appearance. Added accessories in the form of a headpiece, headbands and a pair of earrings inspired by the gandrung omprog dance ornaments and shoulder straps. Overall, the first outfit gives the impression of simple but attractive evening wear with a stylish style for active female aged 20-30 years.

2. Work Description (2)

The second embodiment of evening party clothing for women consists of a peplum skirt, bustier and shawl. Material from luxura satin and chiffon fabric. Embroidered decoration with an *gajah oling* motif and sequins in black, red and gold. The clothing design was inspired by the gandrung ilat-ilat dance costume in the form of black velvet cloth decorated with oling elephants and flowers. In the second clothing design, the ilat-ilat is made along the body from satin fabric decorated with embroidered elephant oling flowers and sequins. Meanwhile, the peplum skirt is decorated with crystal sequins and fringers.

The combination of black clothing with a red scarf plus red, black and gold embroidery and sequin decorations gives an elegant and luxurious impression. The addition of accessories in the form of a headpiece is inspired by the gandrung omprog dance ornament. Overall, the second outfit gives the impression of glamorous and elegant evening wear because of the glowing combination of gold from the embroidery and sequin beads. Overall, the second outfit gives the impression of simple but attractive evening wear with a stylish style for active female aged 20-30 years.

3. Work Description (3)

Trousers made from novus fabric with a peplum variation made from satin combined with a vest made from novos material. The clothing design is inspired by the colors of gandrung dance clothing, red and black. The clothing consists of a vest and peplum

trousers decorated with embroidered *gajah oling* motifs and red, black and gold sequins. Providing a beautiful and luxurious masculine fashion style. Adding accessories in the form of shoulder straps and sipping inspired by Gandrung dance ornaments. Overall, the third outfit gives the impression of masculine and luxurious evening wear for active male aged 20-30 years.

E. Dissemination of Works

After the work is realized, the next stage is the dissemination of the work. This form of dissemination of the work of creating evening wear with embroidered *gajah oling* motifs and sequence, was published through two activities, namely a grand jury and a fashion show. The following is the form of presentation of the work chosen:

1. Grand Jury is the stage of evaluating works in creative works. This activity takes the form of a closed presentation of the designer's work which is then evaluated and given criticism and suggestions by the jury. There are 3 (three) judges in this activity, first jury namely Dr. Dewa Made Weda Githapradana, S. Tr.dS.,M.Sn., second jury namely Dra. Indah Chrysanti Angge, M.Sn. and last jury namely Alphiana Chandrajani Based on the results of the jury's evaluation on May 11 2024, the creation of this work received appreciation for the fabric manipulation applied. For the design concept as a source of ideas, the choice of collection colors, the choice of materials is appropriate, but for design development it still needs to be improved.

2. The final stage is to publish the results of evening wear at a fashion show with a theatrical fashion show concept at the 35th “ANNUAL FASHION SHOW UNESA” held on June 2 2024 start at 17.00 Fashion event the show was held outdoors and collaborated with theater, where not only models walked on the runway, but there was a theatrical performance that told the source of the idea and built an atmosphere from the source of idea was taken from theme “JAGAD OSING” which is the culture of the city of Banyuwangi. This theme is a means of creation and creativity for students in realizing the cultural diversity of the archipelago through fashion works. Carrying the concept of a theatrical fashion show stage, the UNESA Rectorate Joglo was transformed into a runway with magnificent visuals. In each fashion show studio, there is a visual display and opening theater that represents the studio's theme. This event broadcast via social media you tube link: [www.youtube>afsunesa8009](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=afsunesa8009), as well as Instagram and Tiktok.

Conclusion

The final work assignment has gone through several stages of the process of creating fashion works, in accordance with the objectives of the final assignment with the title Banyuwangi *gandrung* dance as a source of ideas for creating evening wear with embroidered *gajah oling* motifs and sequence the authors can conclude the following:

The process of creating the evening wear design was inspired by the Banyuwangi *gandrung* dance with distinctive costumes and ornaments with a combination of red, black and golden clothing colours. Using a work creation method with a practice Ied-research approach through four stages, namely the pre-design or exploration stage, design, realization and presentation which resulted in three evening wear which has the characteristic *gajah oling* motifs on the clothing decoration with embroidery and sequins. The beauty of *gandrung* dance can be seen in the form of evening wear. The results of creating an evening wear design go through several stages, including the preparation stage, which includes taking measurements, making a pattern, and the implementation stage of placing the pattern on the material, cutting the material, sewing and providing decoration and fitting. Next, the presentation of evening wear works presented in a fashion show at the 35th Annual Fashion Show UNESA entitled "JAGAD OSING". The fashion show was held outdoors with the concept of Theatrical Fashion Show on the Floor.

The suggestions related to the creation of the Final Assignment entitled Banyuwangi *gandrung* dance as a source of ideas for creating evening wear with embroidered *gajah oling* motifs and sequence are as follows:

Considering the creation of work holistically, taking into account the philosophical meaning and value of the source of the chosen idea. In addition to evaluating it based on its artistic value, it also values the finished product in order to maintain its original source of inspiration. This can prevent Indonesian culture from being misused for cultural purposes. To optimize the creation of fashion works, a broad understanding is needed so that ideas can be realized. Increased insight can be gained by data collection, interviews, and field research. A planned implementation approach is required in this work. in terms of supplies, equipment, and methods to be applied. As a result, work will be completed faster and with fewer errors or setbacks, meeting the creator's expectations. It is important to carefully consider the philosophical values presented in the work so that it can survive in the future.

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